

DETECTION OF 3-AXIS VIBRATIONS IN FAULTY 3D PRINTERS USING SMARTPHONES AND MACHINE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT: Using 3-axis vibration recording and processing in decision making for fault detection on manufacturing machines is a method that is in increasing usage as it indirectly finds mechanical anomalies in many dimensions. The integration of vibration analysis in 3D printing fault detection has reached significant interest due to its non-invasive nature and real-time monitoring capabilities. This paper explores methodologies and future directions of using vibrations for fault detection in 3D printing processes. Overall results of the three methods: KNN, Insulation Forest and SVM employed to analyze and classify the features extracted from smartphone recorded vibrations data of 3D Printers conclude as prediction from 90% to 100% to the real test data labelled as Faulting or Not Faulting (Before or After the calibration/service/parts replacement/buy a new one).

KEYWORDS: Additive Manufacturing Machines, Fault Detection, 3-Axis Vibrations, Smartphone Sensor Integration, Machine Learning.

1 INTRODUCTION

Machine-tools are critical to production lines, and their reliability directly affects operational efficiency. Fault detection ensures machine health and minimizes downtime. Vibration analysis, particularly 3-axis vibration monitoring, provides comprehensive insights into machine performance by capturing vibrations along the X, Y, and Z axes.

Additive manufacturing is increasingly used in various industries for its versatility and cost-effectiveness (He, H., Zhu, Z. *et al.*, 2024) and additive manufacturing machines are subject to the same problems regarding the level of vibrations.

However, ensuring print quality and minimizing defects remain critical challenges. Traditional fault detection methods include visual inspection, thermal monitoring, and acoustic analysis. This study, using vibrations recorded by a cheap tool - a smartphone, alternatively to other cheap solutions (Kumar, S., Kolekar, T., Patil, S., Bongale, A., Kotecha, K., Zaguia, A., and Prakash, C., 2022) and their analysis, was conducted using the 3D printers of the same type from the Faculty of Industrial Engineering and Robotics, National University of Science and Technology POLITEHNICA Bucharest. The proposed method can be further

used for a large scale of manufacturing machine's fault detection.

2 THE USE OF 3-AXIS VIBRATION RECORDINGS FOR FAULT DETECTION AND SPECIFICALLY FOR 3D COMMON FAULTS

Sensor Technologies Triaxial accelerometers are employed to capture vibrations in three dimensions. These sensors could be placed on critical machine components such as motors, bearings, and gearboxes. For 3D printer's Accelerometers and piezoelectric sensors are commonly used to capture vibration signals. These sensors could be mounted on the print head, build platform, or frame to detect abnormalities. However, this could be an expensive alternative when sensors and related required cost for recording need to be considered.

This is where the availability of the Smartphone 3-axis X, Y and Z vibration as accelerometer comes into duty to easily and cheap perform the recording task thanks to the MATLAB mobile software interface available to record the three channels with the sampling resolution up to 100Hz as described in (MATHWORKS, Sensor Data Collection).

Common machine faults detected include Bearing Failures that could be identified by distinct frequency patterns, Misalignment that could be detected through phase differences in vibration signals, Imbalance able to be recognized by excessive vibrations along specific axes and Gearbox Anomalies diagnosed by irregular vibration signatures during rotation.

Specific faults detected in 3D printers refer to: Layer Shifts detected through abrupt changes in vibration patterns, Extruder Blockages identified by irregular vibrations due to inconsistent material flow and various Mechanical Wear as continuous monitoring reveals gradual changes in vibration signatures, indicating wear in belts, bearings, or motors.

3 VIBRATION DATA ACQUISITION FROM 3D PRINTERS

A series of twelve full working 3D Printers, ZORTRAX M300 PLUS, each having the same printing task were used to record one minute three axis vibration using Smartphone, and MATLAB mobile software that allows either to save the record or stream it in real time. MATLAB Mobile can acquire data from smartphone device sensors. One can analyze the data directly in MATLAB Mobile, MATLAB Online or on a MATLAB session on the desktop as in Figure 1. Anyone can even log sensor data when offline.

The sampling frequency of the recordings was set at 100Hz which is the maximum supported by such a mobile but effective solution.

Fig. 1 A MATLAB Mobile screen showing the smartphone capturing and allowing access to the 3Axis X, Y and Z acceleration/vibrations recording

A total of 45 recordings (one minute three axis vibrations each) from the 12 working 3D printers (9 after successful maintenance and 3 working but having known accuracy problems unsolved due to

the total number of hours in operation) were individually recorded by the same Smartphone successive placement in the same position and orientation on each printer as in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Placement of 3 axis vibration recording Smartphone on 3D Printer ZORTRAX M300 PLUS

The logs files were saved on the server and then downloaded as .mat working space files, from which the three channels representing axes X, Y and Z were saved as time series together with timing. The data was measured as acceleration data using m/s² unit and it was used for further processing and analysis after it was properly grouped and labeled accordingly to the **After** successfully or **Before** or no successful 3D Printers maintenance reparations. Then records were, if necessary, truncated to exactly one minute resulting in a pair of 3 channels of 6000 samples each as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3 The vibration data from the 3 axis represented as channels corresponding: ch1 to X, ch2 to Y and ch3 to Z axis. First faulting 3D Printer record is plotted in blue and first not faulting in red on the same figure.

4 VIBRATION DATA ANALYSIS METHODS

4.1 Feature Extraction

Signal processing techniques, including time domain features as average, standard deviation, and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) are usually employed to analyze vibration signals, (Scheffel, Roberto & Fröhlich, Antônio & Silvestri, Marco., 2021), (W. L. Ng, G. L. Goh, G. D. Goh, J. S. J. Ten, W. Y. Yeong., 2024) and to provide reduced features set to be further used with AI classification algorithms.

In this approach, a total of 45 recordings were used to produce characteristic features for each channel of each recording. A MATLAB software tool called Diagnostic Feature Designer (MATHWORKS, Diagnostic Feature Designer) was used to facilitate computation of thirteen types of

features that could be extracted from time series data, using a variety of commonly known measures, grouped into three categories as in Figure 4. To visualize the distribution per category, a histogram for each feature is plotted in Figure 5.

Feature Type	Feature Name
Statistics features	mean
	standard deviation
	root mean square (RMS)
	shape factor
	higher order kurtosis
	skewness
Impulsive Metrics	Peak value
	Impulse Factor
	Crest Factor
	Clearance Factor
Metrics of Signal processing	Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)
	Total Harmonic Distortion (THD)
	Signal to Noise and Distortion Ratio (SINAD)

Fig. 4 Types and Names of the extracted features

Fig. 5 Histogram of features computed for the three channels respectively: 13 for ch1, 13 for ch2 and 13 for ch3

Feature Ranking: FeatureTable1 X

Fig. 6 Selected Features from 3 channels of Vibration Data Ranked according to the statistical T test

These features were changed according to the ranking, when a faulting signature is included in the usual vibration recorded signal.

Then for each group of recordings faulting or not faulting belonging to the same feature, a statistical T-test was performed to quantify the usefulness of the feature for classes separation. The features were then ranked according to those results and only the first 15 were further saved and used from all channels. These are presented in Figure 6.

4.2 AI methods used to classify features from 3D Printers vibrations and results

Following literature search and previous work in this specific field (Goh, G.D., Sing, S.L. & Yeong, W.Y., 2021), (Liangwei Zhang, Jing Lin, Haidong Shao, Zhe Yang, Biyu Liu, Chuan Li, 2024) the classification decision into faulting or not, based on vibration data and/or extracted characteristic features out of that data, has been successfully carried out with high prediction accuracy by machine learning algorithms such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest (RF) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs).

For the approach described in this paper, the following 3 methods were tested to analyze and classify the features extracted from vibrations data of 3D Printers: K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Insulation Forest (IF) and Support Vector Machines (SVM).

First, the labelled records were split into **Training Set** and **Test Set** by a random partitioning selection having a maximum of 10% of the whole data kept for test purposes including both classes individual records. As the training worked on labeled data, for the test data the label information was first removed but kept into separate array called Test Data Labels. As the number of starting features was 15, it is impossible to plot the state space of all recordings based on all features but for a visual check only the first two ranked were plotted in 2D view in Figure 7.

For every method after the train phase the test set was applied and counted number of True Positives, True Negatives, False Positives and False Negatives. Computed information allows plotting the confusion matrix respectively for KNN, IF and SVM as seen in Figures 8, 9 and 10.

Fig. 7 Two dimensions representations of the first 2 ranked features showing visual classes separation between normal and faulting vibration parameters of 3D Printers.

Fig. 10 Results of the SVM prediction on the vibration features from test set.

Fig. 8 Results of the KNN prediction on the vibration features from test set.

Fig. 9 Results of the IF prediction on the vibration features from test set.

5 DISCUSSIONS, CLAIMING AND CONSTRAINTS

The previously shown results of the three methods applied: KNN, IF and SVM employed to analyze and classify the features extracted from vibrations data of 3D Printers produces a prediction from 90.9% to 100% for the real test data labelled as Not Faulting (After the calibration/service/parts replacement/buy a new one) and a 100% Faulting prediction for all Faulting Machines. The 90.9% score for Not Faulting 3D Printers prediction and 100% for Faulting was achieved only by SVM method, while the other two methods KNN and IF show accuracy of 100% for both cases. Overall, the results confirm that the methodology used for this faulting detection for 3D Printers has achieved its goals and could be considered as a robust, reproducible and trustworthy strategy. As data processing size reduction, there have been tested on two of the models (IF and KNN) the use of just 9 out of the first 15 features and for the same dataset the results were the same, without deteriorating.

The proposed method has the advantage of using existing vibration recording tool, large available and cheap as smartphone and it includes sensors and can use that information for high percentage classify the 3D printer status regarding proper operation or not. This idea overpasses other vibration solutions such as implementing expensive 3-axis vibration monitoring due to high-precision sensors and advanced signal processing algorithms costs implications and does not have to deal with sensor placement as for other methods optimal placement is crucial for accurate fault detection (Isiani,

Alexander & Weiss, Leland & Bardaweel, Hamzeh & Nguyen, Hieu & Crittenden, Kelly, (2023).

Using 3 axis vibration recording and processing data remains of high data complexity as analyzing multi-axis data requires robust computational resources, but it can be done as this research has demonstrated within a reasonable framework. It is possible that in other environments some external vibrations from the environment can introduce noise that can affect measurement accuracy and complicating analysis, issues that must be considered.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

Using 3-axis vibrations in machine-tools and additive manufacturing machine fault detection offers a robust solution for maintaining machine health. Vibration-based fault detection in 3D printing is a promising field with significant potential. The method used has advantages over other attempts regarding the availability of vibration recording device and its simple and robust use. Also compared to other systems using vibrations from accelerometer sensors in 3D Printers faulting recent studies (Michal Blaszczykowski, Dariusz Majerek, Elzbieta Sedziewska, Pawel Tomilo, Jaroslaw Pytka, 2025) it has the fastest way to move recordings to another printer without interrupting the printing process, just place on the same position as the smartphone and start new test. Advances in sensor technology, data analysis, and machine learning will drive future innovations in this field such as this paper started by smartphone use.

As further work to be considered is full integration with IoT providing real-time monitoring and remote diagnostics through all kinds of IoT platforms, advanced machine learning models as use of deep learning for improved accuracy only if necessary and of course any hybrid approaches as combining vibration analysis with thermal and acoustic methods for comprehensive fault detection. A next step to speed up and to large the scale of usage of this paper proposed method will be to use of the smartphone and MATLAB mobile sensors recording streaming facility and to remote send the 3 axis vibrations for real time processing or to run all the tests of a new recording locally on the smartphone using the already trained models and validation which is essential to overcome current challenges and enhance reliability.

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